

Constituents of the Seeds of *Blepharis Edulis*, Pers. Part I.

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Blepharis Edulis, Pers., belongs to the natural order of *Acanthaceae*, and under the local name of *utanjan* and the Persian name *Anjurah*, is sold in the Indian Bazars as a standard Indian medicine. "Medicinally, the seeds are considered to be attenuate, resolvent, diuretic, aphrodisiac, expectorant and deobstruent" (Dymock, *Pharmacographica Indica*, III, 41-42).

The bitter principle of the seeds is described (Dymock, *loc.cit.*) as a white crystalline body, soluble in water, amyl and ethyl alcohol but insoluble in ether and petroleum ether and as giving a red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid, a violet colouration with ferric salts and an agreeable odour of salicylaldehyde on treatment with sulphuric acid and potassium dichromate. The presence of a white crystalline non-bitter principle melting at 225° and giving no colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and ferric salts has also been noticed.

As the result of the present investigation a bitter glucoside *Blepharin* (yield 1.2%), melting at 222° with previous shrinking at 220° and having the formula $C_{16}H_{20}O_{11}$, and a tasteless nitrogenous compound having the formula $C_4H_6O_3N_4$, melting with decomposition at 225-226° with previous darkening in colour at 218° and identified as *dl*-allantoin (yield 2.1%), have been isolated. The isolation of allantoin in more than 2% yield from the seeds of *Blepharis Edulis* is not surprising since it is known to occur frequently in the plant kingdom.*

EXPERIMENTAL.

The seeds of *Blepharis Edulis*, about a year old, were ground to a coarse powder in a grinding machine. When completely burnt it left 7.23% of

cf. Schulze and Barbieri, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1882, *ii*, 25, 145; Fosse, Thomas and Graeve, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 1953; *J. Chem. Soc.*, Abstracts, 1897, *ii*, 118; Plants, *Chem. Zentral.*, 1910, *i*, 1622; Schulze and Booshard, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 9, 420; *J. Chem. Soc.*, Abstracts, 1919, *i*, 60.

a greyish white ash, in which the following elements and radicals were detected: sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, silica, alumina, carbonate, phosphate, chloride, nitrate, and sulphate (in traces). In order to ascertain the general character of the constituents, 50 g. of the powdered seeds were extracted successively in a Soxhlet's apparatus with various solvents in the order given below whereby the following amounts of extracts, dried at 100° to constant weight, were obtained.

1. *Benzene Extract* (3.72%) :— A dark reddish brown thick oil smelling strongly of the seeds was obtained.

2. *Chloroform Extract* (1.02%) :— It was a syrupy brown tasteless extract containing suspended globules of white fatty matter. Its alcoholic solution gave a greenish black colour with ferric chloride showing the presence of tannins and became milky on dilution with water.

3. *Ethyl Acetate Extract* (17.25%) :— It was a brown extract of extremely bitter taste and consisted of a white crystalline mass along with large amount of tannin matter, as it gave black colouration and then a black precipitate with ferric chloride, and a flocculent yellow precipitate with lead acetate solution and reduced Fehling's solution copiously. It gave no colour reactions with alkaloidal reagents.

4. *Alcoholic Extract* (6.04%) :— It was of a syrupy nature and slightly bitter in taste and contained a tasteless white crystalline mass. It reduced Fehling's solution copiously and gave a black colouration with ferric chloride.

5. *Test for Enzymes*.— A quantity (50 g.) of the ground seeds was macerated with distilled water at ordinary room temperature (22°) for 2 days with the addition of a little toluene to prevent bacterial action. The mucilagenous mass was filtered and the filtrate tested as usual for enzymes. Peroxidase, catalase, and invertase were totally absent but diastase was present in minute quantity.

A *preliminary examination* for the presence of alkaloids was made with 200 g. of the powdered drug which was repeatedly extracted with Prollius fluid. The filtrate after concentration was extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid and the acid extract was treated with alkaloidal reagents with negative results.

For complete analysis 9.0 kg. of the powdered seeds were in lots of 0.7 kg. exhaustively extracted with benzene in a 5 litre

extraction flask, the extract concentrated and 342 g. of a thick reddish brown, fragrant, semi-drying oil were obtained. The oil-free powdered drug was extracted with rectified spirit, till a portion of the extract did not leave any appreciable amount of crystalline matter on complete evaporation of the solvent. The combined extract, on concentration on the water-bath to one seventh of its volume and on allowing to stand at ordinary temperature for about a week, deposited a large amount of crystalline matter, which was filtered at the pump. The residue was washed with alcohol until it had assumed a white or at most a light brownish colour. Thus 230 g. of a tasteless and greasy crystalline stuff were obtained, which after repeated extraction with hot benzene in order to remove oily and fatty matter became brown at 210° , softened at 215° and melted at 218° (decomp.). It is tasteless and almost insoluble in all the organic solvents. It was twice crystallised from boiling water as glistening monoclinic prisms, m.p. $225-26^{\circ}$ with previous darkening in colour at 218° . The air-dried substance has the composition $C_4H_6O_3N_4$ and contains no water of crystallisation.

Its solution is not coagulated by tannic acid and does not respond to the ninhydrin reaction of amino acids. It does not reduce Tollen's reagent and Fehling's solution. It does not give any colouration with neutral ferric chloride, nor any precipitate with lead acetate, basic lead acetate, calcium chloride or cadmium chloride. It dissolves in moderately strong mineral acids in the cold to a colourless solution and in dilute ammonia and alkali hydroxides. On heating with concentrated nitric acid no yellow or brown colouration appears. It readily reduces alkaline permanganate even in the cold but acid potassium permanganate only on heating. It evolves ammonia with alkali hydroxides. It does not give positive results in carbylamine, Bulow's, Biuret, and Mureoxide tests. With nitrous acid it evolves nitrogen. It gives with mercuric nitrate a white precipitate which is soluble in boiling water. [Found: C, 30.83, 30.51, 30.47; H, 4.08, 3.98, 3.79; N, 35.9, 35.6; M. W. (ebulioscopically in water), 131, 135. $C_4H_6O_3N_4$ requires C, 30.42; H, 3.8; N, 35.4 per cent. M. W. 150).

Action of Concentrated Nitric acid.—30 C.c. of concentrated HNO_3 ($d 1.4$) was gradually poured on to the powdered substance (3 g.) when it first puffed up and then crumbled to powder. The excess of acid was evaporated on the water bath—when a slightly sticky granular stuff was left behind, which crystallised from a small quantity of boiling alcohol in fine tiny needles. The air-dried crystals fused at 200° to

an opaque mass, evolved gas at 200-210° and turned deep brown and decomposed at 225° and were identified as those of allanic acid. (Found in sample dried at 125°: C, 23.29; H, 2.51; N, 34.72. $C_4H_5O_5N_5$ requires C, 23.65; H, 2.46; N, 34.48 per cent). The silver salt, prepared by the usual method, darkened at 195° and decomposed at 199°. (Found: Ag, 34.94. $C_4H_4O_5N_5Ag$ requires Ag, 34.83 per cent). The solution of the substance (2 g.) in the smallest amount of ammonium hydroxide was allowed to stand in open air for several days. On complete evaporation of water ammonium allantoate was obtained as a crystalline powder. (Found: C, 24.72; H, 5.80; N, 36.9. $C_4H_{11}O_4N_5$ requires C, 24.86; H, 5.70; N, 36.37 per cent). By the action of aqueous caustic potash or soda and subsequent precipitation with absolute alcohol potassium or sodium allantoate were obtained. (Found: C, 22.21; H, 2.78. $C_4H_7O_4N_4K$ requires C, 22.42; H, 2.60 per cent). (Found in a sample dried over calcium chloride: C, 22.01; H, 4.34. $C_4H_7O_4N_4Na, H_2O$ requires C, 22.22; H, 4.16 per cent).

Preparation of Allantoin.—20 G. of uric acid were suspended in 400 c.c. of water and dissolved by the careful addition of caustic soda in small quantity at a time and with constant stirring. The alkaline solution was treated with a 5% solution of 13 g. of potassium permanganate and well stirred. As soon as the solution was decolourised it was filtered from manganese dioxide and the filtrate acidified with acetic acid and evaporated (best in vacuo) until crystals appear. After three crystallisations from hot water it melts at 225° (decomp.) after previous darkening in colour at 218° and this remained undepressed by admixture with the non-bitter principle. (m.p. of allantoin 229° recorded in literature).

Isolation of Blepharin.—The filtrate and washings after the separation of allantoin were concentrated and allowed to stand for a few days, but crystals did not appear. It was then repeatedly extracted with hot ethyl acetate, after a few extractions with hot benzene till the syrupy mass was no longer bitter. The ethyl acetate layer was decanted from the heavy viscous syrupy mass and was concentrated to one seventh of its volume and on allowing to stand for a week became semi-solid due to the separation of glistening tiny needles which were filtered off at the pump after thinning with a mixture of ethyl alcohol and ethyl acetate (1 : 4). Some more of the crystalline stuff was obtained from the filtrate and washings after concentration and allowing to stand for a number of days. After removal of oily

and fatty matter by extraction with hot benzene, it was repeatedly crystallised from hot alcohol till the air dried material melted at 219-20° with previous shrinking at 213°. After two crystallisations from acetone it was obtained as glistening stout needles and the air-dried material melted at 220° after shrinking at 220°. It is proposed to name this bitter principle as *Blepharin*.

It is sparingly soluble in cold water and more soluble in boiling water. It is slightly soluble in cold acetone, amyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, methyl alcohol and fairly in the hot. It is insoluble in ether, petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform, bromoform and carbon tetrachloride. Caustic alkali and alkali carbonate solutions have no action on it. It gives no precipitate in aqueous or alcoholic solution with silver nitrate, calcium chloride, ferric chloride, lead acetate, or copper acetate. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gives no colouration in the cold but a purple red colouration appears immediately on warming. With concentrated sulphuric acid containing 1% potassium dichromate it gives a fine violet colouration in the cold; while with concentrated sulphuric acid containing sufficient potassium dichromate it gets carbonised and gives the odour of burnt sugar. With ferric chloride in aqueous or alcoholic solution it gives no colouration and reduces Tollen's reagent and Fehling's solution only after hydrolysis with dilute mineral acids. With alcoholic caustic potash it does not give any colouration in the cold or on heating.

To a quantity of the substance (0.01 g.) in water (1 c.c.) 2 drops of a solution of α -naphthol (10% in chloroform) and 1 c.c. of concentrated H_2SO_4 were added when a reddish violet ring and on shaking a bluish violet precipitate was formed (Molisch's test). A small quantity of blepharin, dissolved in acetic anhydride, gave on addition of a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid a pinkish violet colouration which deepened on standing (Liebermann's cholesterol reaction). To its solution in glacial acetic acid, 1 c.c. of chloroform and a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were added when a permanent pink colour appeared (Hager-Salkowski reaction). It gave a negative Keller-Killiani reaction. [Found (in sample dried at 120-125°): C, 48.94, 49.03; H, 5.39, 5.41; M.W. in phenol (cryoscopic) 306, 330; $C_{16}H_{20}O_{11}$ requires C, 49.5; H, 5.16 per cent. and M. W. 388].

The ethyl acetate mother liquor which did not deposit any more crystal and still had an intensely bitter taste was evaporated to remove ethyl acetate and the residue dissolved in water with constant stirring and the solution treated with a solution of lead acetate. The result-

ing greyish yellow precipitate was filtered off, well washed first with hot water and then with alcohol and after decomposition with hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic suspension gave a reddish brown solution. After removal of sulphuretted hydrogen by a current of carbon dioxide and on concentration under reduced pressure it deposited no crystalline mass. It was extracted with benzene which removed a trace of fatty matter and extractions with chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone did not result in the isolation of any crystalline matter. The alcoholic solution on complete removal of the solvent left a dark brown sticky mass which consisted mostly of catechol, tannins and saponins, since on shaking it with water a large amount of foam resulted. It gave an intense blue colouration on addition of potassium ferricyanide containing a little ferric chloride, and a black colouration and then a precipitate with ferric chloride, a red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid, reduced Tollen's reagents on warming, and mercuric chloride on long heating precipitated gelatine from solution and gave a greenish white precipitate with tartar emetic and a deep red colouration with potassium ferricyanide and ammonia.

The aqueous filtrate and washings from the afore mentioned lead acetate precipitate gave a yellow precipitate on treatment with excess of basic lead acetate. This on being worked up as before gave a brown alcoholic solution from which on concentration no precipitate separated.

The aqueous filtrate from the above basic lead precipitate was treated with hydrogen sulphide and the light yellow filtrate after separation of lead sulphide was concentrated on the water bath to a small volume and was found to contain besides a large excess of glucose and acetic acid a small amount of a crystalline substance which has not yet been obtained in sufficient quantity. The mother liquor reduced Fehling's solution copiously and on treatment with phenylhydrazine an osazone was formed which was found to be identical with phenylglucosazone, m.p. 206°.

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Further work on the elucidation of the constitution of biepharin is in progress.

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